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Marital Disharmony and Academic Adjustment of Secondary School Students in Uyo Local Education Committee

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Abstract

This study aimed at determining the relationship between marital disharmony and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee. Two purposes and two research questions guided the study. A correlational survey design was adopted for the study, while the population of this study consisted of all 6,603 senior secondary two (SS2) students in the fifteen (15) public secondary schools in the study area. A sample size of 378 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students was selected for the study, representing 5 percent of the study population, using Taro Yamane sampling formulas. A self-structured questionnaire titled "Marital Disharmony and Academic Adjustment of Secondary School Students Questionnaire (MDAASSSQ)" was used for data collection. Data generated were analysed using Pearson Product

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Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics, and the finding revealed a very high positive and significant relationship between communication issues in marriage, financial disagreement, and the academic adjustment of secondary school students in the study area. A conclusion was drawn from the findings, and the researchers recommended, among other things, that husbands and wives should strive to maintain a friendly, happy, and peaceful family environment, avoiding painful conflicts that could lead to emotional and behavioural problems affecting students' academic adjustment.

Keywords: Marriage, Marital Disharmony, Academic Adjustment

Introduction

Marriage is a basic institution in every society. In every complete society governed by law, marriage exists as a public legal institution and not merely a private romantic declaration or religious rite. An institution that offers legitimacy to sexual relationships and reproduction for legitimate children. Marriage involves joining in matrimony two individuals of different genders to become one flesh as husband and wife, given the need for companionship, procreation, and continuing and sustaining family ties. Nevertheless, marital instability in present-day society is of immense concern, as it is associated with separation, divorce and widowhood.

Marriage is a legalising of a special relationship between a man and a woman to which the society gives approval, and it places partners under legal and social obligations to each other and the society. The family is the household and those who live in one house and a network of persons such as the couple, their offspring and kin intimately held together by a bond of social and kinship relationships. According to Lesmin and Sarker (2008), marital disharmony is the major cause of marital instability in the society. The author defined marital disharmony as a situation in which there are disagreements and unpleasant feelings between the husband and wife, which can result in marital instability. Marital disharmony can occur if the spouses do not spend sufficient time together or if they do not have common interests. Sexual dissatisfaction

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with regard to various factors such as frequency, quality, interest, and enjoyment of the spouses, as well as extramarital affairs, may cause marital distress or problems.

Hence, the increasing incidence of marital disharmony such as the occurrence of divorce shows that there is marital instability in several families in the Nigerian context. Marital disharmony, according to Omorogiuwa and Omorogiuwa (2016), occurs as an attempt of one individual or partner to checkmate the behaviour and anticipations of the other. Marital disharmony threatens the household stability as well as the well-being of the children, as it often impacts their academic adjustment and achievement. The family stability often has a marked influence on the students' motivation for learning and on her to cope with academics. The home environment is a strong pointer to the academic adjustment and achievement of children. This is because a number of children's academic potentials are now confronted with increasing difficulties as a result of parental marital disharmony. The contact between the parents, teachers and students makes a lot of impact on the academic performances of the students. Castro-Martin and Bumpass (2009) found that those who do not regularly attend classes because of a lack of proper monitoring by the parents could experience challenges adjusting academically. Parents are thereby faced with the problem of enriching their home environment to establish a positive effect on the student's academic performance in schools.

Statement of the Problem

Strains in marriage interaction between couples living together are becoming common. In the Uyo Local Education Committee, the researcher observed that marital disharmony is on the rise because of communication issues, culture and tradition, infidelity, lack of trust, and economic depression among couples. As a result, anger, resentment, dissatisfaction, frustration and hopelessness take control of the relationship and at times break down the marriage irretrievably. These could threaten societal values and the academic adjustment of students.

It is disheartening to observe that in the Uyo Local Education Committee of Akwa Ibom State, some students usually roam the streets during school hours,

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committing deviant offences such as bullying, stealing, drug abuse, cultism, smoking, assault, and excessive aggression against other students. Some students go as far as fighting teachers and parents. The rate of indiscipline and lack of respect for elders, parents, teachers and constituted authorities is alarming. Negative gang activities, such as cultism, are noticed on a regular basis.

Although many researchers have studied factors related to marital disharmony and students' academic adjustment, they have not examined the specific variables addressed in this study or focused on the present study area. Therefore, the present study sought to fill this gap by determining the relationship between marital disharmony and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between marital disharmony and the academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee. Specifically, the study sought to determine the following:

- i. The relationship between communication problems in marriage and the academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee.
- ii. The relationship between financial disagreements between spouses and the academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the relationship between communication problems in marriage and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee?

- ii. What is the relationship between financial disagreement and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee?

Theoretical and Conceptual Review

The Structural Theory of Marital Stability

The structural theory was propounded by Minuchin in 1974. The theory states that marital problems arise where the personality of one partner is swallowed up by the personality of the other partner, and problems also come up where one partner's interest is in conflict with the general interest in the marriage. It is a theory that focuses on marital stability, especially where one partner in the marriage has the irrational tendency to impose his or her wishes on the other partner and when his or her manner of approach to marital stability is panic-stricken.

The structural theory model places emphasis on marital stability when a problem arises and when couples find it impossible to interact positively in their relationship. It is a well-known theory for family and marital counselling, as it proposes that marital stability should be promoted so that it does not affect the social, academic and moral development of children. According to the theory, marital stability can only be achieved when one member's interest is in harmony with the general interests of the marriage. The sense is that people who are in a relationship or who wish to be in a relationship should ensure that the interests of one partner do not affect the other partner negatively, which can bring about marital disharmony to the general benefit of the relationship.

The theory of differential association is relevant to this work as it explains that marital disharmony can affect both the family members and the academic adjustment of children. The theory has clarified the fact that children learn to adjust positively to academic work through parents during the process of interaction or communication. A child needs to be taught moral values from parents in order to develop good behaviour and live a responsible life. If parents fail to model good behaviour and inculcate moral

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values into children's minds, the young ones may likely exhibit deviant behaviour and fail to adjust positively to the demands of academic activities.

Concept of Marital Disharmony

Academic and social exposure can either strengthen or weaken marital relationships. When couples lack adequate academic and social enlightenment, they may be more vulnerable to disharmony, misunderstandings, and the misinterpretation of issues within their marital life (Iheagwam, 2011). Marital disharmony, according to Ezeilo (2010), occurs when the suppression of feelings within the family becomes severe and when members are unable to effectively communicate their emotions.

Similarly, Omorogbe, Obetoh, and Odion (2010) describe marital disharmony as a situation in which communication between spouses becomes impaired and the husband-wife relationship is disrupted. Such disruption often results in tension, mistrust, doubt, reduced emotional closeness, limited sharing, decreased intimacy, and feelings of isolation. Consequently, spouses may become involved in negative experiences such as disagreements, quarrels, discord, friction, antagonism, and open conflicts, which are common characteristics of marital disharmony.

Marital disharmony may also arise when couples associate with individuals who influence them to adopt unhealthy approaches to resolving marital conflicts. Ibeh (2013) identified several additional causes of marital disharmony, including breach of trust, age at marriage, sexual deprivation, conflicts related to marital roles and finances, fertility challenges, and infidelity. Furthermore, in-laws and other external influences can exert either positive or negative effects on marital relationships. When in-laws impose excessive authority or interference in a marriage, it may generate resentment from either partner's family, thereby contributing to marital conflict. Gossip, criticism, and blame from in-laws or other external parties can also intensify tensions and lead to friction between spouses.

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Concept of Academic Adjustment

Academic adjustments are modifications to how students participate in classes and activities, which allow students to meet academic goals and expectations. Academic adjustments give students equal access to the educational opportunities. Academic adjustment also refers to students' ability to develop their coping skills and learning strategies aimed at achieving satisfactory academic results. According to Salami (2011), academic adjustment is the process of making friends, inclusion in campus life and social networking. It comprises those experiences that help to connect students to the school environment and aid in their psychosocial development. Malinga-Musamba (2014) added that academic adjustments are those experiences in academic life that contribute to students' overall satisfaction in their new environment, which promotes intra-personal growth.

Academic adjustment is important in helping students who may face problems related to language, finance and poor social support and have difficulties in adapting to their new roles. Students achieve academic adjustment through reaching a state of satisfaction with their academic performance, friendships with peers and teachers and the environment as a whole. It involves experiences that support academic development, encourage cognitive development, and enhance academic motivation in a meaningful way (Al-Khatib, Awamleh and Samwi, 2012). Academic adjustment involves the ability to be resilient in different settings. Brinkworth, McCann, Mathews and Nordstrom (2009) suggested that this relies on the ability of the student to make a quick adjustment to an environment, which requires greater autonomy than was expected in a school setting. This can be achieved through internalising the character, culture, and behavioural norms of the institution. The students' ability to set goals and achieve a balance between academic and social activities plays a critical role in their success and, ultimately, in their chances of graduating.

Communication Issues in Marriage and Students Academic Adjustment

'Communication issues in marriage' refers to some form of friction, disagreement, or discord arising between the husband and wife (Animasahum, 2014). Such conflict

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usually arises when the beliefs, decisions or actions of both parties are either resisted or unacceptable (Malek, 2013). Violence between the husband and wife has some emotional implications. This is because emotions can quickly intensify discord. Family couples are expected to be involved in long-term relationships where mutual understanding and peaceful interaction prevail. If such a relationship is full of painful discord, it may likely lead to divorce or domestic violence, which is often fuelled by fighting between husbands and wives, sibling rivalry, parent-child power struggles, quarrelling among family members, spouse nagging, disagreement, and others.

Many families face difficult struggles that are often quite volatile and troubling. According to Animasahum (2014), discord is found in every kind of family, and it can reach extreme levels sometimes where the husband and wife fight each other. The author further added that adolescents who witness family violence face increased risk for such emotional and behavioural problems as anxiety, depression, poor school attendance and performance, low self-esteem, disobedience, nightmares and physical health complaints. Such emotional and behavioural problems sometimes make students show deviant acts such as being violent with students and teachers, cheating in examinations and disrupting the activities of the school.

In a study conducted by Gorman-Smith and Tolan (2008), the author noted that children are more likely to lose positive academic adjustment and resort to violence if severe conflict always occurs in their family. Families where these situations are in place will become unbalanced and unhealthy and fail to function normally, as difficult behaviours may result in one or all of the members of the family. Abdul (2016) further found that unpeaceful communication in marriage between couples reduces the likelihood of students becoming poorly adjusted to school life.

Financial Disagreement and Students' Academic Adjustment

Disagreement over financial spending may result in marital disharmony. Money and financial conflict have been one of the primary factors that eventually lead to separation and divorce as well as affecting children's social and academic wellbeing. Money is something that must be talked about before marriage; hence, many couples

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fail to do so. Financial problems within a family can lead to one spouse overspending, being stingy with finances, or feeling like they know better than their spouse on how to handle the monthly bills. Kamau (2013) stated that money has been found to be the topmost reason for dispute among secondary school teachers. Management of finance in a family can also instigate conflict among couples and hinder the stability of marriage.

Disagreement over financial spending may exert a negative influence on the academic adjustment of students in the school. In accounting for the relationship between financial disagreement and academic adjustment of students, Cummings and Davis (2014) noted disagreement over financial spending affects the children's academic adjustment directly through emotional stress and academic performance. A conflict-riddled marriage may be associated with low achievement of children because witnessing conflicts keeps them from focusing on schoolwork. Most times, disagreement over financial spending hinders the financing of children's education as well as the provision of adequate school learning materials for children. These children also learn inappropriate social problem-solving skills through modelling parental behaviours.

In a study conducted by Lee and Chung (2014), the authors found that financial disagreement has a strong association with students' school adjustment because such students are always in distress and distracted from academic work. The authors added that students of unstable homes due to financial issues scored lower than children from stable marriages on measures of academic success. In another study conducted by Inanga and Esther (2018), the authors found that families with severe financial issues are most likely to breed children who lack the ability to adjust to school activities and vice versa.

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Research Method

Research Design

The correlational survey design was adopted for the study. This design is used whenever a researcher wants to find out the magnitude and direction of the relationship that exists between the dependent and independent variables (Udoh and Joseph, 2005). Therefore, this design was considered suitable for this study because it enabled the researcher to measure the relationship between marital disharmony and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all the 6,603 senior secondary two (SS2) students in the fifteen (15) public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State (Secondary Education Board, Research and Statistics Division 2021).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 378 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students was selected for the study, representing 5 per cent of the study population, using Taro Yamane sampling formulae. To get adequate sampled schools, the random sampling method was used to select 9 public secondary schools out of 15. Subsequently, 42 students were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools using the hat-and-draw method, resulting in a total of 378 respondents.

Instrumentation

A self-structured questionnaire titled “Marital Disharmony and Academic Adjustment of Secondary School Students Questionnaire (MDAASSSQ)” was used for data collection. The items were framed in line with the research questions and hypotheses. The instrument had two parts. Section (A) contained 15 items, that is, 5 items each on marital disharmony, while section (B) contained 8 items measuring academic adjustment of students. MDAASSSQ was measured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4; Agree (A) = 3; Disagree (D) = 2; Strongly Disagree (SD) =

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1. The respondents were requested to give their own opinions or views on the instrument using the symbol (\surd).

Validation of the Instrument

To ensure the face validity of the instrument, two copies were submitted to two validators from the Department of Educational Foundations, Guidance and Counselling at the University of Uyo. The validators assessed the suitability and clarity of the items contained in the instrument. Their observations, suggestions, and corrections, along with those provided by the researcher's supervisor, were incorporated in producing the final version of the instrument used for the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

To establish the reliability of the instrument, the Cronbach Alpha reliability technique was used. Here, the instrument was administered to 40 SS2 students in a selected school not included in the population sample. The instrument was administered, and data were collated. Data was subjected to correlation, and Cronbach's alpha statistics were applied for testing the internal consistency of the instrument. This yielded the overall reliability coefficient of .82 for marital disharmony and .73 for items measuring students' academic adjustment, respectively. This index, according to Udoh and Joseph (2005), is a high reliability index since the reliability coefficient is above .50. Therefore, the instrument was deemed reliable for use in the study.

Method of Data Collection

The research instruments were personally administered to the respondents in their respective schools by the researcher together with two trained research assistants. In addition to items written on the questionnaire, the subjects were given verbal instructions and clarifications where necessary. All the 378 copies of questionnaires administered were filled properly according to instructions and collected instantly to avoid any loss.

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Method of Data Analysis

Data generated were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions. The same statistical tool (PPMC) was used for testing the null hypotheses by comparing the r-value with the critical r-value to determine the significance of the relationship between variables, all at the 0.05 level of significance. The research questions were answered using the decision rule for answering questions in a correlational study, as presented by Uzoagulu (2011) as follows:

Coefficient (r) - Relationship

± .00 to ± .20 – Negligible, weak, very low, little or none.

± .21 to ± .40 - Present, slight, but low.

± .41 to ± .60 - Average, moderately high, fairly high

± .61 to ± .1.00 - Very high

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between communication issues in marriage and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee?

Table 1: Correlation analysis of responses on the relationship between communication issues in marriage and academic adjustment of secondary school students

Variables	N	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Remark
		$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$			
Communication Issues in Marriage	378	5768	90682			
Students' Academic Adjustment	378	12256	404126	190757	0.88	Very High Positive Relationship

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The result in Table 1 shows a very high positive relationship between communication issues in marriage and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee. This is shown by the correlation coefficient of 0.88. The implication of this result is that students are most likely to be well adjusted to academic activities if mutual understanding and peaceful interaction exist among husbands and wives.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between financial disagreement and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee?

Table 2: Correlation analysis of responses on the relationship between financial disagreement and academic adjustment of secondary school students

Variables	N	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-	Remark
		$\sum y$	value $\sum y^2$			
Financial Disagreement	378	5771	90021			
Students' Academic Adjustment	378	12256	404126	189292	0.73	Very High Positive Relationship

The result in Table 2 reveals a very high positive relationship between financial disagreement and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee. This is shown by the correlation coefficient of 0.73. This implies that students would be well-adjusted academically if financial issues were adequately managed.

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Discussion of Findings

The researchers presented a combined discussion of the findings from both the research questions and the hypotheses tested.

Results from research question one and hypothesis one revealed a very high positive and significant relationship between communication issues in marriage and the academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Gorman-Smith and Tolan (2008), which revealed that children are more likely to lose positive academic adjustment and may even resort to violent behaviour when severe conflicts frequently occur within the family. Families experiencing such situations often become unstable and unhealthy, thereby failing to function normally, as problematic behaviours may emerge in one or more family members.

This finding also aligns with the study conducted by Abdul (2016), which indicated that unpeaceful communication between couples in marriage increases the likelihood of students becoming poorly adjusted to school life. Therefore, the finding suggests that persistent misunderstandings and conflicts in marital communication can negatively influence students' academic adjustment.

Results from research question two and hypothesis two revealed a very high positive and significant relationship between financial disagreement and academic adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Education Committee. This finding is in agreement with the finding of the study conducted by Lee and Chung (2014). The authors found that financial disagreement has a strong association with students' school adjustment because such students are always in distress and distracted from academic work. This finding is also in line with that of Inanga and Esther (2018), whose finding showed families with severe financial issues are most likely to breed children who lack the ability to adjust to school activities and vice versa. It is, therefore, observed from this finding that disagreement over financial spending may hinder the financing of children's education as well as the provision of adequate school learning materials for children, hence affecting students' academic adjustment negatively.

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Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it is therefore concluded by the researcher that inadequate management of communication issues in marriage, financial disagreement, as well as the relationship between parents and their children can result in students' inability to adjust academically in schools.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made from the finding of the study:

- i. Husbands and wives should always maintain a friendly, happy and peaceful life within the family and ensure that painful conflicts that could cause emotional and behavioural problems to students' academic adjustment are avoided.
- ii. School counsellors should intensify efforts in counselling parents through PTA meetings on issues of financial management and communication stability.
- iii. Parents should ensure that they maintain a good relationship such that the children can easily approach them and disclose their feelings or thoughts. This will go a long way in reducing the tendency of students to become deviant in schools.

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